

Emails, Links, Profiles, and Verifications: Study of Google and Facebook about Login Access

Arjun Dahal

Mental Asylum of Education

Gauradaha-3, Jhapa

P.O.Box 1

Abstract:

We use emails to create profiles, and even though we would prefer third party sites, then too we need some basic tools, recognized by third party sites. In this paper, we have discussed about emails and verifications, adding other emails to profiles, and user access (beginning from login in, and logging out)

Introduction:

In any profiles, if there are services available, to add another emails; I don't know, if other people do, or don't add emails, but I do add emails. And while using add email features, problems were seen in accounts especially for login, in my Facebook profiles arjundahal001, and arjundahalard.

I had changed the name username of my facebook profile arjundahalard to arjundahal001, after Phishing activity was seen, and then created another new facebook profile with username arjundahal001, then changed it to arjundahalard.

In that respect, both of my username are same, as I relied on using same user name, by changing among two accounts, keeping same username.

Now let us look at the first picture.

It says, if my account is mine or not.

Now let us look at another picture, which too asks same, if my profile is mine or not.

10:26 AM

37

m.facebook.com/arjund

1

10:24 AM

37

m.facebook.com/login/

1

PLACES LIVED

Add city

Kathmandu, Nepal

Current City

Jhapa, Nepal

Hometown

CONTACT INFO

EDIT

Facebook

/arjundahalard

Email

arjundahalard384@gmail.com

BASIC INFO

EDIT

Birthday

February 11, 1996

Gender

Male

OTHER NAMES

+ Add a nickname, a birth name...

RELATIONSHIP

facebook

Continue as Arjun?

We couldn't find an account matching the login info you entered, but found an account that closely matches based on your login history.

Arjun Dahal

arjundahalard384@gmail.com

Continue

Not You?

In these pictures, question about login are asked, inquiring, if it is me or not.

10:27 AM 📶 37%

🏠 m.facebook.com/arjund 1 ⋮

← Arjun Dahal

Arjun Dahal

Passionate in Physics, Mathematics, Music, Literature, and Philosophy.

[✎ Edit Profile](#) ⋮

 What's new, Arjun?
Let's update some profile info that may have changed.

[Not Now](#) [Update Profile](#)

Studied Theoretical physics at Tri

10:27 AM 📶 37%

🏠 m.facebook.com/?stype 1 ⋮

facebook

Choose Your Account

 Arjun Dahal ⚙️

[+](#) Log Into Another Account

Which account did you log out of?

Sometimes, people accidentally log into the wrong account. Help us understand why you logged out quickly.

[My Account](#)

[Wrong Account](#)

10:28 AM

36

Arjun, log into Facebook with one click Inbox ☆

F Facebook 10:25 AM
to me ^

From Facebook • security@facebookmail .com

Reply-to noreply • noreply@facebookmail.com

To Arjun Dahal • arjundahalard .thereason@gmail.com

Date Jun 14, 2021, 10:25 AM

Standard encryption (TLS).
View security details

f Facebook

Hi Arjun,

We noticed you're having trouble logging into your account. If you need help, click the button below and we'll log you in.

11:02 AM

35

one click Inbox ☆

F Facebook 10:25 AM
to me ^

From Facebook • security@facebookmail .com

Reply-to noreply • noreply@facebookmail.com

To Arjun Dahal • arjundahalphysics@gmail .com

Date Jun 14, 2021, 10:25 AM

Standard encryption (TLS).
View security details

f Facebook

Hi Arjun,

We noticed you're having trouble logging into your account. If you need help, click the button below and we'll log you in.

Log In With One Click

11:02 AM

📶 📶 📶 📶 35

Welcome Back to Facebook

Inbox

Facebook 9:54 AM
to me ▾

arjundahalard284@gmail.com

Welcome Back to Facebook

Hey Arjun,

The Facebook account associated with arjundahalard384@gmail.com was recently reactivated.

If you were not the one who reactivated this account, please visit our [Help Center](#).

[Go to News Feed](#)

[Help](#)

This message was sent to arjundahalard384@gmail.com at your request.

Here are few other pictures, which shows about linking accounts, and notification send by Facebook, in all three of my Gmail accounts, as I had linked them, though I am not sure about, arjundahalard384@gmail.com, if I had linked it or not.

I used these pictures, as the email notifications didn't had mentioned any confidentiality, like seen in many emails, which are talked as per confidentiality, urging either to delete when concernedness lacks or to keep email safe.

Problems:

I found problems does arises based on active accounts, and deactivated accounts, like shown in pictures, which mentions that there is another email similiar to that of my email, and even that email was of mine.

I don't know if that was problem (account activation and deactivation) which I faced, while attempting to log in two different accounts, but just got being logged in account with username arjundahal001.

Further Problems:

How would Facebook work, when same emails are added to both? Would account be accessed by any of emails provided by adding emails, or topics of primary and secondary email would play role? I found Google uses aliases , and I have used it as well, hoping to link accounts, based on primaryness and secondaryness, whereas recovery email too are talked. I have added all of my emails to [Orcid](#) , and it would again be question, that would I be able to access Orcid, by means any emails added and verified in my profile. And my facebook profiles,

[First Facebook Profile](#), [Second Facebook Profile](#) too would be an important question, unless merged, putting questions about accessing, and recognizable means of accessing, like as email, mobile numbers, or username for lot of other social platforms.

Actknowledgegement:

Pictures shown in this paper is author's work, as per his facebook profile, and I don't know if I should write it as I or we (singular and plural), my actknowledgegement goes to Facebook, as it is widely used, and I do do use it oftenly.